

Information specialist support to EPOC LMIC authors

The Norwegian EPOC satellite Cochrane Information Specialist (CIS) can normally provide the following support to review authors from low and middle-income countries

All authors are urged to try to develop draft search strategies and discuss these with the CIS

To authors that do have local access to library services

1. Advice on databases and other sources to be searched
2. Advice on how to develop a search strategy
3. Feedback on authors' search strategies
4. Advice on how to report the search process
5. CIS will "sign off" the reporting of the search process before publication

To authors that do not have local access to library services

1. Advice on databases and other sources to be searched
2. Advice on how to develop a search strategy
3. Feedback on authors' search strategies
4. Develop a protocol search strategy once a draft protocol has been submitted
5. Develop and run search strategies in selected databases accessible to the EPOC satellite once a final protocol has been approved by the contact editor
6. Reviews in process that exceed one year from search date need to rerun all search strategies before publication, however not before a final review has been approved by the contact editor
7. Peer review of search strategies by a second information specialist
8. Creation and maintenance of an EndNote Library with all importable records retrieved
9. Provision of records retrieved as:
 - An EndNote Library file
 - Text files - if possible, in preferred format depending on the author's reference management tool (RefMan, ProCite, EndNote, or other)
 - Reference lists (Word document)
10. A search log documenting searches performed by the CIS, including the database name, database host, database time span, date searched, number of records retrieved for each database, and a record of each search strategy used by the CIS
11. Report or advice on how to report the search process
12. CIS will "sign off" the reporting of the search process before publication

The following support will not normally be provided

1. Removal of duplicate records from different searches will be provided only if time allows
2. Full text of articles will only be provided in exceptional circumstances

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